

**INFLUENCE OF LIBRARY USER EDUCATION IN ACADEMIC
LIBRARIES: A CASE OF UNIVERSITY OF ILORIN AND
LAUTE CH.**

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Abstract

This study focused on influence of user Education Programme on the use of University Libraries in Nigeria a case study of Universities of Ilorin and Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso Libraries. Questionnaire was designed and used to elicit responses from 280 students selected from different faculties in the two Universities.

Findings from the collected data, revealed that the students from both University agree that user education should be designed within the context of each course and provision of adequate and qualified manpower resources should be ensured to assist users locating materials. Also, user education programme should be made ICT driven to make the study realize its objectives.

INTRODUCTION

Library is a very important part of academic institutions. According to Robertson (1992), a library is an agency, which engages in collection, organization, processing, preservation and dissemination of recorded information in the various formats. The library is a component part of the history of civilization and this is why it is sometimes described as social memory of human civilization. It always has an assumed responsibility to its immediate environment. The basic needs to which libraries respond in society, are those of education, research, information, civic responsibility, aesthetic appreciation and recreation.

The University library is meant to meet the objectives of the University environment it serves, that is, the curriculum of the institution. The National Policy on Education (2004) stated the aims of University education as:

- a. The acquisition of basic physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to develop into useful members of the community.
- b. The development of the intellectual capacities of individuals to understand and appreciate their environments and
- c. The acquisition of an object view of the local and external environments.

Popoola (2000) asserted that information is knowledge communicated or received by a user that has some forms of values to him. He submitted that information is the fifth factor of production. The reason being, that the world economy is information driven with a substantial amount of the available documentary information being in the form of grey literature, especially in the developing countries.

The need for library user education programme for students was introduced so as to ensure effective use of the library. also, because of the exponential growth of published materials, both in their chosen field and other fields, the growth in published materials particularly in the science, technology and medicine requires that scattered information in various formats be properly disseminated through information literacy programme for students.

Library user education programme is a form of education for library users. It is meant to help users to make maximum advantage of library resources to meet their information needs. The instructional programme is variously referred to as User Education, User Instruction, Library Skills, Library Instruction, Bibliographic Instruction and Library Orientation. . In 1970's, Library Use Instruction in the 1980's and information literacy in the 1990's. Lwehabura (1999) says although these terms may differ, they refer to the same concept which is . an organized programme practices across various types of libraries to enable library users acquire skills which would allow them to use library resources effectively and become information literate.

Statement of the Problem

User education programmes are instituted in various institutions of higher learning with a view to helping students on how to make effective use of the library facilities as an essential information service unit. As the issue of poor performance of students in information literacy programme in library. "Library use" worry the librarian. Garba (2004), explained that the basic philosophy of the information literacy programme is to impact skills of library use on the students. This would

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enable them identify, locate, retrieve and exploit information resources from the library.

The major problems that agitated the mind of this researcher are:

It has however been observed that despite the fact that the use of library is an aspect of General studies course, University students exhibit low level of information seeking skills and behaviour;

This study will therefore focus on how information literacy programme affect students effective use of library resources and lack of standard in the integration of information literacy programme as an important aspect of library education to facilitate effective students study habit and research. The study therefore intends to find out why the use of library is poor.

Purpose

- To examine the effect of implementing the programme on students use of the library.
- To find out the ways in which user education are being carried out, and if there is any differences between the two Universities.
- To find out students use of ICT in relation to user education.

Research Questions

1. What forms of user education programmes exist in the two universities under study?
2. To what extent does the user education programme in the universities influence the students use of their libraries?
3. Is the use of ICT included in the user education programme?
4. To what extent does the user education programmes influence the students' use of ICT infrastructure in their universities?
5. What problems are encountered by the students in the user education programme in their universities?
6. What strategies can be adopted to overcome such problem?

Research Hypotheses

To guide the study, the following hypotheses were formulated.

1. There is no significant relationship between user education programme and students use of library in their universities.
2. Relationship between user education programme and students use ICT infrastructure.

3. There is no significant relationship between user education programme and problems encountered by student in the programme.
4. There is no significant difference in the type of problems encountered in the user education programme by the students of Universities of Ilorin and Lautech.

Significance of the Study

The study is hoped to:

- reveal the proper framework of user education that would bring positive change to the handling of the programme.
- It would lead to improved information seeking skills or behavior of the library users especially the university students.
- The findings will serve as a base for further studies it will be beneficial to librarians in the teaching of the programme.

Literature Review

Fjallbrant (1998) explains that the goals and objectives of user education in academic library must be in agreement with the general aims of the library. According to him, the aims must be related to the goals and objectives of higher education, while Unomah (2004) sees the objectives of user education as that much at the end of the programme students should be able to use their university and other libraries in connection with their studies and future work. Furthermore, he stated that students should see the library as a place to work and to borrow materials, experience, interest and enjoyment in the process of obtaining information. An example of goals and objectives of an academic library in Nigeria should be that a student graduating from a Nigeria University should have necessary library skills to undertake research at post graduate level.

In Nigeria, different types of methods are used to dispense information and knowledge to the learners, these range from lectures, seminars/ demonstrations, guided tours, to self-instruction, each of these methods has merit and demerit. However, a good method of instruction should be capable of achieving the following:

1. Sufficiently motivate the student, enable the student to relate new work to existing knowledge.

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2. Make it possible for the student to control the rate of flow of instruction. Instructional librarians should aspire to use methods that are capable of combining as many of these qualities as possible.

According to librarian grossary (1990), the most common teaching used in library instruction is the chalkboard, supported by transparency for illustrations. Slides are used as alternatives to transparency in some libraries.

Methodology

Two faculties were selected from both universities of Ilorin and Lautech they have highest number of students population.

A proportionate stratified random sampling technique was adopted in selecting 10% from both university respectively as in table 4.1 to form a total sampling size of 280 students used for the analysis.

Name of University	Years	Faculties	Population
Unilorin Proportion	3	Medical Science Education	600 850 1450 x 10% = 145
Lautech Proportion	3	Engineering and Environmental Science	628 720 1348 x 10% = 135
		Total	280

Results

The summary of the Analysis of the two university were discussed with the use of frequency counts and percentage. This is shown in the table below:

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Table 4.2: T-test Analysis showing difference in the ways User Education is being carried out between students of UNILORIN and LAUTECH.

Variable	No	Mean	Std	Df	Cal. t-value	t-value
UNILORIN	109	3.2624	.77541	265	.023	1.960
LAUTECH	158	3.2646	.7646			

Table 4.2 shows that the calculated t- value is 0.23 while the table t- value is 1.960 with 265 degree of freedom and at '0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated t- value is less than the table t- value, hypothesis is hereby accepted, that is, there is no significance difference in the ways user education is being carried out between students of UNILORIN and LAUTECH.

H₀: There is significant effect of students user. education programme on the use of ICT facilities in the two Universities. This is shown in the table 4.4

Table 4.3: T-test Analysis showing the effect of students information literacy programme on students use of ICT accessories.

Variable	No	Mean	Std	Df	Cal. t-value	t-value
UNILORIN	109	3.2454	.8312	265	.299	1.960
LAUTECH	158	3.2753	.7826			

Table 4.3 shows that the calculated t- value is 0.299 while the table t- value is 1.960 with degree of freedom and at 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated t- value is less than the table t- value. Hypothesis 2 is hereby accepted that there is no significant effect on students use of ICT accessories in UNILORIN and LAUTECH as a result of user education.

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H₀₃: There is no significance relationship between students use of user education skills and the use of library in UNILORIN. This is shown in the table below:

Table 4.4: Pearson 'r' analysis showing relationship between students use of information literacy skills and the use of library in UNILORIN.

Variable	No	Mean	Std	Df	Cal. t-value	t-value
Students' use of information literacy skill	109	3.2954	.7730	108	.98	.1946
use of library	109	3.2539	.7879			

Table 4.4 shows that the calculated r- value is 0.988 while the table r-value is .1946 with 108 degree of freedom and at 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated r-value is greater than the table r-value, therefore hypothesis 3 is rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted, that is, there is no significant positive high relationship between students use of information literacy skills and the use of library.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between students use of information literacy skills and the use of library in LAUTECH. This is revealed in the table 4.6

Table 4.5: Pearson 'r' analysis showing relationship between students use of information literacy skills and the use of library on LAUTECH.

Variable	No	Mean	Std	Df	Cal. t-value	t-value
Students' use of information literacy skill	158	3.1582	.8622	158	.982	.1946
use of library	158	3.2699	.7700			

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Table 4.5 shows that the calculated r-value is 0.982 while the table r-value is .1946 with 158 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated r-value is greater than the table r-value, therefore hypothesis 3 is rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted. That, there is a significant positive high relationship between students use of user education- skills and the use of library.

H₀₅: There is no significance difference in the type of problems encountered by the students of UNILORIN and LAUTECH in the course of undertaking user education programme in relation to the use of library.

Table 4.6: T-test analysis the types of problems encountered in the course of undertaking information literacy programme in your institution.

Variable	No	Mean	Std	Df	Cal. t-value	t-value
Unilorin	109	3.3372	.7640	265	.797	1.960
Lautech	158	3.2627	.7416			

Table 4.6 shows that the calculated t-value is .797 while the table t-value is 1.960 with 265 degree of freedom and at 0.05 level of significant. Since the calculated t-value is less than table t-value, hypothesis 5 is accepted. That is, no significance difference in the types of problems encountered in the course undertaking information literacy programme in the two universities (Unilorin and Lautech).

H₀₆: There is no significant difference in the remediation procedures to help the students of Unilorin and Lautech in overcoming the problems of the use of library accessories through effective management of user education programme. This is shown in table 4.7

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Table 4.7: T-test analysis showing remediation procedures to help the students to overcome problems encountered.

Variable	No	Mean	Std	Df	Cal. t-value	t-value
Unilorin	109	3.3633	.7799	265	2.056	1.960
Lautech	158	3.1658	.7652			

Table 4.7 shows that the calculated t-value is 2.056 while the table- value is 1.960 with 265 degree of freedom and at 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated t- value is greater than the table t- value, hypothesis 6 is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. That, there is significance difference in the remediation procedures to help the student to overcome problems encountered. This is in favour of University of Ilorin. This can be seen by comparing the mean of the two variables (Unilorin and Lautech) University of Ilorin has a mean 3.3633 while that of Lautech is 3.1658.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding reveals that there is no significant difference in the ways user education is being carried out between students of Unilorin and Lautech. It shows that there is no different ways in locating information

The second finding reveals that there is no significant difference in the effect of students user education programme on students use of ICT accessories in the two universities. The study therefore, show that virtually all the student in the two universities have access to the use of ICT accessories in their - institution because the ICT accessories were made available and human resources are available to put them through it.

The third finding reveal that there is a significant positive relationship between students use of user education skills and the use of library in Ilorin and Lautech. The result also confirmed that the level of use of library is highly impressive among the student. This is perhaps due to high level of users awareness and availability of ICT accessories

The fourth finding reveals that there is no significant difference in the types of problems encountered in the course of undertaking user education programme in both institution. It shows that the students have similar problem facing the programme such as inadequate exposition to information literacy and non-challant attitude of libraries are some of the problems.

The fifth finding reveals that there is no significant difference in the remediation procedures to help the students of Unilorin and Lautech in overcoming the problems of the use of library accessories through effective management of user education programme. It shows that the same procedure can be used to overcome the problems such as making the course compulsory, adequate orientation, organized lecture on how to use the library and assisting in locating the right materials at the right time. The study showed that user education programme allowed the students to acquire more information literacy when they go to the library, during orientation and when they use handbooks and during the Course class.

Conclusion

It was found out that the use of user education programme was in favour of University of Ilorin and Lautech. This can be seen by comparing the means of the two variable, (Unilorin and Lautech). It can be concluded that a study of user education programme is an essential programme which provides the students with basic knowledge on how to use Online- public Access Catalogue, CD-ROM, Internet services and how to use all these ICT accessories conveniently.

Recommendations

With the above finding and conclusion the following recommendations are proffered.

1. That adequate number of competent and qualified manpower should be provided to teach library user education as this is highly essential to make the programme realize its objectives.
2. The effectiveness of user education programme depends mainly on the availability of ICT infrastructure in each higher institution, so more ICT infrastructure should be provided.
3. The management staff should be designed within the context of each course i.e inline with their subject combination.

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